

SYNTHESIS IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART I. N-SUBSTITUTED-2-METHOXY-5-CHLORO-9-AMINOACRIDINES

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N-substituted 2-methoxy-5-chloro-9-aminoacridines have been described. 2-Methoxy-5-chloro-acridine and 2-methoxy-5-chloro-9-aminoacridine have also been prepared.

The use of acridine derivatives as antimalarials was first marked by Mauss and Mietzsch (*Klin. Woch.*, 1933, 12, 1276), who introduced Atebrin [2-methoxy-6-chloro-9(ω -diethyl-amino-isoamylamino) acridine dihydrochloride]. Magidson and Grigorowski (*Chim. Farm. Prom.* No. 1, 26) later prepared acriquine [2-methoxy-6-chloro-9 (γ -diethylamino-propyl) aminoacridine dihydrochloride] which also was found to be equally potent. Since then a great number of acridine compounds have been synthesised. Amongst these, the various 9-aminoacridines, especially those with a basic substituent in the amino group are of therapeutic importance, particularly from the standpoint of antimalarial value.

Magidson and Grigorowski (*Ber.*, 1936, 61, 396) have established that the presence of both methoxy and chloro groups in the acridine nucleus is essential for the development of antimalarial properties. When either of the groups is absent, the compound is devoid of antimalarial value. Feldmann and Kopelivitch (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, 273, 488) have shown that by the transfer of chlorine atom from position 6 to 7, the antimalarial activity is considerably reduced. No information is as yet available as to the antimalarial characteristic of chlorine atom at position 5 or 8. Similarly it would be of interest to ascertain how the antimalarial properties are affected by shifting the methoxy group from position 2 to that at 1, 3 or 4 in the acridine molecule.

It was therefore decided to attempt the preparation and to investigate the antimalarial properties of basically N-substituted derivatives of the sixteen possible methoxy-chloro-9-aminoacridines, out of which fourteen are unknown.

The present paper deals with the preparation of various N-substituted 2-methoxy-5-chloro-9-aminoacridines.

2-Bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid has been condensed with *o*-chloroaniline to give 6'-chlorodiphenylamine-4-methoxy-2-carboxylic acid, which on treatment with excess of phosphoryl chloride is converted into 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine. This is condensed with seven dialkylamino alkylamines, sulphanilamide and arsanilic acid. The various 2-methoxy-5-chloro-9(diakylamino-alkyl) aminoacridines are better obtained through the 6'-chlorodiphenylamine-4-methoxy-2-carboxyl chloride (*cf.* E.P., 364, 392; Goodall and Kermack, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1546; and also Drozdov, *J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1938, 8, 1192). The reaction proceeds very smoothly and excellent yields are obtained,

2-Methoxy-5-chloroacridone and 2-methoxy-5-chloro-9-aminoacridine have also been described.

The various condensation products show strong fluorescence in dilute alkali, alcohol, acetone or ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Bromo-5-methoxybenzoic Acid.—*m*-Methoxybenzaldehyde, obtained by methylation of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (Tiemann, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2048) on bromination gave 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzaldehyde which was oxidised to 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid (Pschorr, *Annalen*, 1901, 391, 26).

4-Methoxy-6'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—Dry 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid (23.1 g., 1 mol.) was added to a solution of potassium (1 atom) in methyl alcohol (30 c.c.) and then freshly distilled *o*-chloroaniline (19.2 g. 1.5 mols) was added. Copper powder (0.1 g.), CuCl (0.1 g.) and *iso*amyl alcohol (30 c.c.) were added and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 2-3 hours and methyl alcohol allowed to evaporate off slowly from a short air condenser. Excess of *iso*amyl alcohol was then distilled off and the last traces removed by passing steam. The residue after being made acidic to Congo red was crushed to a green powder. It was extracted with potassium bicarbonate (charcoal) and decomposed with hydrochloric acid yielding a voluminous yellow mass. After drying, it was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as bright yellow needles, m.p. 186°-88°, yield 75%. It is soluble in ether, chloroform, hot benzene and toluene. (Found: N, 4.95. C₁₄H₁₂O₃NCl requires N, 5.04 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxyl Chloride.—Phosphorous pentachloride (2.30 g., 1.1 mol) was added to a suspension of 4-methoxy-6'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (2.78 g., 1 mol) in absolute petroleum ether (40-60°, 80 c.c.) and the reaction mixture refluxed on a water-bath for about 20 minutes, when a clear yellow solution was obtained. This was filtered and the filtrate on cooling deposited a yellow mass. This was filtered and washed with a little petroleum ether. Finally it was crystallised from low-boiling absolute petroleum ether as long orange yellow needles, m.p. 112°, yield 70%. (Found: N, 4.63. C₁₄H₁₁O₂NCl requires N, 4.73 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5 : 9-dichloroacridine.—4-Methoxy-6'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (5 g.) was refluxed with phosphoryl chloride (40 c.c.) for about 4 hours at 130°. Excess of phosphoryl chloride was removed under vacuum and the yellow sticky residue was taken up in chloroform (40 c.c.). The solution was cooled externally in ice and treated with an excess of 10% ice-cold ammonia solution. The chloroform layer was thoroughly washed with water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Chloroform was distilled off and the residue was crystallised from absolute ethyl acetate (charcoal) as beautiful yellow plates, m.p. 157-58°, yield 85%. It shows a strong bluish fluorescence in ethyl acetate. (Found: N, 5.20. C₁₄H₉ONCl₂ requires N, 5.03 per cent).

γ -Diethylaminopropylamine, γ -di-*n*-propylaminopropylamine, γ -di-*n*-butylamine-propylamine, γ -di-*n*-amylaminopropylamine and γ -piperidinopropylamine, were each prepared by the reduction of their corresponding nitrile obtained by the interaction of acrylic nitrile and the appropriate secondary amine (Adam *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 727). While Adam and co-workers have carried out the catalytic reduction

of these nitriles with only moderate yields, we have carried out these reductions by sodium and absolute ethanol with much higher yields. In each case the product was characterised by its picrate. The following general method has been used for the reduction of basically substituted nitriles.

Sodium (cut into small pieces, 10g.) was added slowly with continuous shaking to a solution of the nitrile (10 g.) in absolute ethanol (250 c.c.) kept boiling on a water-bath. After cooling, the reaction mixture was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. Sodium chloride was filtered off and washed with a little absolute ethanol. The combined filtrates were fractionated under vacuum. After all the alcohol had been removed, the residue in the flask was decomposed with 50% sodium hydroxide solution and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried (fused magnesium sulphate), ether was distilled off and the residue distilled under vacuum. The products were in each case free from the corresponding secondary amines, a common impurity obtained during the catalytic reduction. γ -Diethylaminopropylamine was obtained in 78% yield against that of 54% by Adam and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). It may be noted here that Hamilton and Utermohlen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 156) who tried the reduction of γ -diethylaminopropionitrile with sodium in toluene and water, have reported negative results. γ -Di-*n*-butylaminopropylamine was obtained in 75% yield (Adam and co-workers give 32% yield). Burekhalter and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 2012) give 70%. γ -Di-*n*-amylaminopropylamine was obtained in 68% yield (Adam and co-workers give 47%). γ -Piperidinopropylamine was obtained in 88% yield, against that of 68.5% by Adam and coworkers.

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine.— γ -Diethylaminopropylamine (1.5 g.) was added slowly to a solution of 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine (3 g.) in phenol (12 g.). The reaction mixture was heated at 100–110° for 3 hours. After cooling, the contents were poured into excess of 2*N*-sodium hydroxide solution and the product extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was shaken with 25 c.c. of 5% acetic acid and aqueous layer removed. It was filtered from any suspended acridone and decomposed with alkali. The yellow base was extracted with ether and ethereal extract dried over fused potassium carbonate. The dihydrochloride of the condensation product was precipitated by addition of alcoholic hydrochloric acid. The semi-solid dihydrochloride, so obtained, was twice crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a deep yellow powder. It was dried in an air-oven at 100° for 3 hours, m.p. 240–42° (decomp.), yield 50%. It is freely soluble in water and alcohol. (Found: N, 9.40. $C_{21}H_{26}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 9.44 per cent).

The same compound was obtained in 75% yield, when the reaction was carried through the acid chloride.

A solution of 4-methoxy-6'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxyl chloride (2.80 g., 1 mol.) in absolute benzene (20 c.c.) was treated with γ -diethylaminopropylamine (1.35 g., 1 mol.). The yellow solution at once changed to a colourless syrup. The mixture was warmed for 10 minutes on a water-bath and benzene was then removed under vacuum. The residual oil was refluxed with phosphoryl chloride (5 c.c.) for about 2 hours, after which excess of phosphorous oxychloride was removed under vacuum. The yellow product dissolved in water to give a clear solution. No insoluble acridone was obtained. It

was decomposed with alkali and the base extracted with ether and converted into dihydrochloride as described above.

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(γ -diethylaminobutyl) aminoacridine was obtained by either of the two methods described above, by the condensation of 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine and δ -diethylaminobutylamine (Strukove, *Khim. Farm. Prom.*, 1933, 332).

The dihydrochloride was twice crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ether as a yellow powder, m.p. 245-47° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{22}H_{28}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 9.16 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(ϵ -diethylaminoamyl) aminoacridine was obtained by the condensation of 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine and ϵ -diethylaminoamylamine (Magidson *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 396). The dihydrochloride could not be crystallised as an oil always separated on the addition of ether to the alcoholic solution. It is very soluble in water and alcohol. The dipicrate was prepared in benzene solution and crystallised from absolute ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 180-82°. [Found: N, 15.01. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_3Cl$, 2($C_6H_3N_3O_7$) requires N, 14.69 per cent].

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(γ -di-n-propylaminopropyl) aminoacridine.—The dihydrochloride was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a yellow powder, m.p. 308-10°. It was dried in an air-oven at 100° for 3 hours. (Found: N, 8.55. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 8.88 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(γ -di-n-butylaminopropyl) aminoacridine.—The dihydrochloride was twice crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ether as a yellow powder. It melted above 310° with decomposition and previous darkening. (Found: N, 8.55. $C_{23}H_{34}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 8.39 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(γ -di-n-amylaminopropyl) aminoacridine.—The dihydrochloride was crystallised from absolute alcohol as light yellow glistening leafy plates, which exhibit green fluorescence in alcohol. It darkens at 300° and melts with decomposition at 325-27°. (Found: N, 7.62. $C_{27}H_{30}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 7.95 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(γ -piperidinopropyl) aminoacridine dihydrochloride was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a yellow powder, m.p. 253-55° (decomp.). It is soluble in water and alcohol. (Found: N, 9.23. $C_{22}H_{26}ONCl_2$, 2HCl requires N, 9.20 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-(p'-sulphanilaminophenyl) aminoacridine.—A solution of 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine (2.78 g., 1 mol.) in phenol (8 g.) was treated with p'-aminobenzenesulphonamide (1.72 g., 1 mol.). The mixture was heated at 100° for 3 hours. After cooling, it was diluted with ether (50 c.c.) and the yellow hydrochloride of the condensation product was filtered and washed with ether. It was then triturated with 15% cold ammonia solution. The orange product obtained, after drying, was crystallised from absolute alcohol as orange needles, which turn yellow on heating, m.p. 250-51°. (Found: N, 10.10. $C_{20}H_{16}O_3N_3ClS$ requires N, 10.15 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9(p'-arsonophenyl) aminoacridine.—A solution of 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine (2.78 g., 1 mol.) in phenol (8 g.) was treated with p'-arsanic acid (2.17 g., 1 mol.) and the reaction mixture heated at 100-110° for 3 hours. After cooling, it was diluted with ether (70 c.c.) and the orange product, so obtained, was collected on suction and thoroughly washed with it. It was then washed with boiling water to remove any

uncondensed arsanilic acid. The condensation product was dissolved in 5% potassium hydroxide solution and filtered free of any acridone. It was decomposed with dilute acetic acid and then recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as stout orange needles, m.p. 257-59° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.92. $C_{20}H_{16}O_4N_2ClAs$ requires N, 6.10 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloroacridone.—2-Methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine (0.2 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (20 c.c., 5 g.) for about 30 minutes, when the yellow acridine changed slowly into white acridone. It was filtered and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 269-70°. It shows a bluish fluorescence in acetic acid. (Found: N, 5.45. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.39 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-chloro-9-aminoacridine.—A solution of 2-methoxy-5:9-dichloroacridine (2 g.) in phenol (15 g.) was treated with ammonium carbonate (1.5 g.) at 70° and the temperature raised to 130° and maintained for 15 minutes. After cooling, the reaction mixture was diluted with ether (80 c.c.) and dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed into the mixture, when the hydrochloride separated out. It was filtered and washed successively with ether and acetone. The hydrochloride was decomposed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and the yellow product so obtained was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and acetone as deep yellow glistening needles, m.p. 230-32°. It is soluble in acetic acid with a strong bluish green fluorescence which persists even on dilution. (Found: N, 10.78. $C_{14}H_{11}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 10.83 per cent).

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